

VOCABULARY LEVEL AND READING COMPREHENSION: A STUDY OF GRADE 6 LEARNERS IN CLUSTER 3 OF TUMAUNI SOUTH DISTRICT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15195048>

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between vocabulary level and reading comprehension among Grade 6 learners in Cluster 3, Tumauni South District. A descriptive research design was employed involving 110 Grade 6 students from Lapogan, Liwanag, and Lalauanan-Sto. Non-elementary schools. Two questionnaires were administered to determine respondents' vocabulary levels and reading comprehension. Data were analyzed using frequencies, percentages, and chi-squared tests. The results revealed that 55% and 56% of the respondents had low vocabulary levels for stories 1 and 2, respectively. Similarly, 53% and 49% of respondents had low reading comprehension levels for Stories 1 and 2, respectively. A significant relationship was found between the vocabulary level and reading comprehension ($X^2=16.87, p < 0.05$). Furthermore, a significant relationship was observed between the percentage of words not understood by the respondents and their reading comprehension ($X^2 = 24.84, p < 0.05$). These findings suggest that vocabulary knowledge strongly influences reading comprehension and that a higher percentage of unfamiliar words leads to lower comprehension. This study highlights the importance of vocabulary development in enhancing reading comprehension skills among Grade 6 learners. These results can guide educators in designing targeted interventions and literacy programs to improve both their vocabulary and reading abilities in this specific context.

Keywords: *Academic Achievement, Grade 6 learners, Linguistic comprehension, Reading Comprehension, Vocabulary*

INTRODUCTION

Vocabulary and reading comprehension skills are crucial for academic success, particularly among elementary school students. Research has consistently shown that these skills are foundational to learning across various subjects and have long-term effects on educational outcomes. Working memory, inhibition, and cognitive flexibility have been found to have direct and indirect effects on reading comprehension of both narrative and expository texts for fourth-grade students (Escobar & Espinoza, 2024). Additionally, academic vocabulary serves as an important mediating variable between executive function and reading comprehension, highlighting the interconnected nature of these skills (Escobar and Espinoza 2024). For English as a Second Language (ESL) learners, syntactic awareness and metacognitive reading strategies have been identified as significant predictors of academic reading comprehension (Nergis 2012). Interestingly, the importance of vocabulary and reading comprehension skills extends beyond English-language learners. A study on Spanish-English bilingual elementary students found that vocabulary depth contributes significantly to English reading comprehension (Leider et al., 2013).

Research has consistently demonstrated a strong link between vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension across various age groups and education levels. Meta-analyses and longitudinal studies have shown that vocabulary knowledge is a significant predictor of reading comprehension (Dong et al., 2020; Hjetland et al., 2020). In early childhood, vocabulary and grammar skills form a linguistic comprehension pathway that directly influences reading comprehension development (Hjetland et al., 2020). This relationship persists throughout primary school, where vocabulary knowledge contributes to a large proportion of the variance in text comprehension (Dong et al., 2020). Studies of adolescents and adults have revealed an inverted U-shaped correlation between vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension across educational stages (Dong et al. 2020). Interestingly, the relationship between vocabulary and reading comprehension remains unclear. For students with limited reading vocabulary, certain morphological skills (e.g., syntactic and phonological/orthographic knowledge) may play a compensatory role in supporting reading comprehension (Goodwin et al., 2020). Ellorin and Anselmo et al. (2024) explored educators' perspectives on pedagogical innovation and technology integration in modern classrooms. Their findings suggest that incorporating digital tools and innovative teaching strategies can significantly enhance students' engagement and comprehension skills, particularly in language learning. Integrating such approaches in the Tumauni South District may provide a pathway for improving vocabulary acquisition and reading comprehension among grade 6 learners. Further investigation is needed to examine the connection between vocabulary proficiency and reading comprehension among sixth-grade students in this district for several compelling reasons. First, the district may possess distinctive demographic, economic, and educational features that could uniquely influence this relationship compared to other areas. Second, gaining insight into this local-level connection can assist educators in customizing their instructional approaches to tackle specific vocabulary and comprehension obstacles faced by students in the district. Moreover, targeted studies can illuminate how factors,

such as linguistic diversity, resource availability, and local curriculum implementation affect vocabulary acquisition and reading comprehension. This study may also uncover gaps in current teaching methods and guide the creation of focused interventions to enhance both vocabulary and reading abilities. Ultimately, a more profound understanding of this relationship within the context of sixth-grade students in this district could result in more efficient literacy programs, enhanced academic achievement, and improved readiness for future educational challenges.

The research gap this study aims to address regarding the relationship between vocabulary level and reading comprehension of Grade 6 learners can be inferred from the existing literature: Several studies have established a strong correlation between vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension across various educational stages (Babayiğit & Shapiro, 2019; Dong et al., 2020). However, the specific relationship for Grade 6 learners was not explicitly addressed in the context provided. Research has indicated that vocabulary knowledge consistently predicts reading comprehension, but its contribution may vary across grade levels (Yovanoff et al., 2016; Yovanoff et al., 2005). Interestingly, some studies have suggested that the relationship between vocabulary and reading comprehension is not linear. For instance, Dong et al. (2020) found an inverted U-shaped correlation across educational stages, whereas Schmitt et al. (2011) observed a relatively linear relationship between vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension. This discrepancy highlights the need for further investigation, particularly focusing on Grade 6 learners. This study examined the relationship between vocabulary level and reading comprehension for Grade 6 learners in Cluster 3, Tumauni South District. This study investigates the relationship between vocabulary level and reading comprehension among Grade 6 students in Cluster 3, Tumauni South District. The study sought to determine the vocabulary and reading comprehension levels of the respondents, examine the correlation between these two variables, and explore the potential impact of unfamiliar words on reading comprehension. The research hypothesizes that there is no significant relationship between the respondents' reading comprehension and their vocabulary level, as well as no significant relationship between the percentage of words not understood and reading comprehension performance.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design used in this study was descriptive. Descriptive research is conclusive in nature, rather than exploratory. This implies that the quantifiable data were examined and described. This design involves observing and describing the behavior of the subject without influencing it in any way. Descriptive research is suited to the study because it determines the relationship between vocabulary level and reading comprehension of Grade 6 learners selected elementary schools in Cluster 3, Tumauni South District.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in Cluster 3 of the Tumauni South District, namely, Lapogan, Liwanag, and Lalauanan-Sto. Nino, Elementary Schools, Tumauni South District, Tumauni, Isabela. Pilitan and Paragu Elem Schools were not included in the study because of their distance. Cluster 3 of Tumauni South District is located at the gateway of the municipality of Tumauni. Lapogan Elementary School is located at the heart of its community. The school provides active strategies and techniques, even when public institutions are located far from the center of the municipality. Liwanag Elementary School is located in the midst of a barangay. The school offers a dynamic teaching-learning process that can provide knowledge and information to young and active learners of this generation. Lalauanan Elementary School is an easy-to-locate school situated in the middle of its community. Learning institutions provide commendable processes and methods for teaching young learners. Tumauni South District, Cluster 3, is a performing school that creates an energetic and dynamic learning atmosphere.

Selection of the Respondents

The study involved 110 Grade 6 students from Lapogan, Liwanag, and Lalauanan-Sto. Non-elementary schools. This is the total number of grade 6 students in the aforementioned schools.

Data Gathering Instrument

To determine the Relationship of Vocabulary and Reading Comprehension level of Grade 6 Learners in Cluster 3, Tumauni South District, questionnaires were used for data gathering. Two types of questionnaires were used: one to ascertain or determine the learners' vocabulary level and the other to establish their reading comprehension level. The questionnaires were obtained from a grade 6 English Book.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before conducting the study, the researcher sought permission from the office of the School Division Superintendent through channels. He also communicated with school principals. When permission was granted, he went to different schools and, with the aid of the pupils' advisers, administered a reading comprehension and vocabulary test to the respondents.

Statistical Treatment of Data

After administering the test, he tabulated and interpreted the data using the following statistical tools. Frequencies and Percentage this were used in determining the number of the Respondents within different score ranges for vocabulary and reading comprehension. The chi-square test was used to test the null hypothesis that there was no significant relationship between the vocabulary level and reading comprehension of the respondents and the percentage of words not understood.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered on the Relationship of Vocabulary Level and Reading Comprehension of Grade 6 Learners in Cluster 3, Tumauni South District.

Table 1 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to their Vocabulary Level

SCORE RANGE	QUALITATIVE DESCRIPTION	STORY 1		STORY 2	
		F	%	f	%
9-10	High Level	0	0	0	0
6-8	Average Level	14	13	9	8
3-5	Low Level	61	55	62	56
0-2	Very Low Level	35	32	39	36
TOTAL		110	100	110	100

Presents the vocabulary levels of the Grade 6 students. The data show that there are 61 respondents (story 1), 55%, and 62 respondents (story 2) or 56% who are within the score range of 3-5 or Low Level and 35 or 32% (story 1) and 39 or 36% (story 2) are within the score range of 0-2 or Very Low Level. None of the patients received a score within the 9-10 score range. This means that none of the respondents had a high level of vocabulary. The data implied that the vocabulary level of the respondents was below the average level.

McKeown et al. (2018) described an intervention to teach academic words to middle school students, including sixth-graders. This study found that instructed students showed improvement in word knowledge, lexical access, and morphological awareness.

Table 2. Distribution of the Respondents According to Their Reading Comprehension Level

SCORE RANGE	QUALITATIVE DESCRIPTION	STORY 1		STORY 2	
		F	%	f	%
9-10	High Level	0	0	0	0
6-8	Average Level	19	17	16	15
3-5	Low Level	58	53	40	36
0-2	Very Low Level	33	30	54	49
TOTAL		110	100	110	100

The data presented in the table shows the distribution of respondents according to their reading comprehension levels for the two stories. For both stories, the majority of respondents had low and very low levels of reading comprehension. For Story 1, 53% of respondents scored in the low-level range (3-5 points), while 30% scored in the very low-level range (0-2 points). Only 17% achieved an average level score (6-8 points), and none of the respondents reached a high level (9-10 points). Similarly, for Story 2, 36% scored

in the low-level range and 49% in the very-low-level range. Only 15% achieved an average score, with no high-level score. These results are consistent with the findings of several studies on reading comprehension. For instance, Katrancı and Kuşdemir (2016) reported that participants' reading comprehension was medium, and they were not competent enough to detect the main idea in narrative and informative texts. Snyder and Downey (1991) also highlighted differences in reading comprehension skills between reading-disabled and normally achieving participants, which could explain the distribution observed in the table. In conclusion, the data reveal a concerning trend in reading comprehension levels, with the majority of respondents scoring in the low to very low range. This underscores the importance of targeted interventions and strategies to improve reading comprehension, such as those discussed in James et al. (2020) and 9, which emphasize the roles of morphological awareness, vocabulary, and integrated reading comprehension strategies in enhancing reading skills.

Table 3. Results of Significant Relationship Between the Vocabulary Level and Reading Comprehension of the Pupils

Variables	Computed Value Of χ^2	Tabular Value Of χ^2	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Vocabulary Level And Reading Comprehension Of The Pupils	16.87	9.49	$\chi^2_c > \chi^2_t$	Reject H_0	Significant

Results of the significant relationship between pupils' vocabulary level and reading comprehension It is evident from the results that the computed value of $\chi^2 = 16.87$ is greater than the tabular value of $\chi^2 = 9.49$. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected at a significance level of 0.05. Thus, there is a significant relationship between the pupils' vocabulary level and reading comprehension. This implies that pupil vocabulary level strongly affects reading comprehension. It is further inferred that students comprehend what they read well when they have better knowledge of their vocabularies. This confirms Calderon's assertions of Kintsch¹, that vocabulary development is the key to reading comprehension development.

Is there a significant relationship between the percentage of words not understood by the respondents and their reading comprehension?

Table 4a. Number of Words Not Understood by the Respondents

No. of Words Not Understood	STORY 1		STORY 2		2 STORIES	
	F	%	f	%	f	%
61 ABOVE	1	1	1	1	1	1
46-60	1	1	0	0	1	1
31-45	5	5	13	12	9	8
16-30	55	50	31	28	43	39
0-15	48	43	65	59	56	51
Total	110	100	110	100	110	100

shows that the majority of the respondents understood most of the words in both stories. For Story 1, 93% of the respondents understood all but 0-30 words, while for Story 2, 87% understood all but 0-30 words. Across both stories, 90% of the respondents understood all but 0-30 words. Interestingly, Story 2 appeared to have been slightly easier to comprehend, with 59% of respondents understanding all but 0-15 words, compared to 43% for Story 1. This suggests that the vocabulary used in Story 2 may have been more familiar to the participants, or that the context provided better support for understanding unfamiliar words. In conclusion, the data indicated that the majority of respondents had a good understanding of the vocabulary used in both stories, with only a small percentage struggling with more than 30 words. This aligns with research showing that shared storybook reading can be an effective method of vocabulary acquisition (Brett et al., 1996). However, it is important to note that factors such as reading style, story repetition, and the number of target words can moderate word-learning effects (Flack et al., 2018).

Table 4b. Results of Significant Relationship Between the Percent Of Words Not Understood By the Respondents and their Reading Comprehension

Variables	Computed Value Of X^2	Tabular Value Of X^2	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Percent of Words Not Understood by the Respondents and their Reading Comprehension	24.84	12.59	$X^2_{c} > X^2_t$	Reject H_0	Significant

The results presented in the table indicate a significant relationship between the percentage of words not understood by respondents and their reading comprehension. This finding aligns with the research of Schmitt et al. (2011), who explored the connection between vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension. The study found a relatively linear relationship between the percentage of vocabulary known and degree of reading comprehension (Schmitt et al., 2011). Interestingly, while the table suggests a significant relationship, it does not provide information about a specific threshold or cut-off point for vocabulary knowledge. This contrasts with the findings of Schmitt et al. (2011), who suggested that 98% vocabulary coverage is a reasonable target for readers of academic

texts. Additionally, Zhang and Zhang (2020) reported that vocabulary knowledge accounts for 31%-45% of the variance in L2 comprehension, highlighting the importance of vocabulary in reading comprehension. In conclusion, the significant relationship between words that are not understood and reading comprehension underscores the crucial role that vocabulary knowledge plays in comprehension. This aligns with broader research findings that consistently demonstrate a strong correlation between vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension across various studies and languages (Jeon & Yamashita, 2014; Zhang & Zhang, 2020). These results emphasize the importance of vocabulary instruction and development in improving reading comprehension skills.

Conclusions

This study revealed a significant relationship between vocabulary level and reading comprehension among Grade 6 learners in Cluster 3, Tumauni South District. The majority of students demonstrated low levels of both vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension. A strong correlation was found between these two variables, indicating that students with higher vocabulary levels tended to perform better on the reading comprehension tasks. Additionally, the percentage of unfamiliar words in a text significantly affects students' comprehension, with a higher number of unknown words leading to lower comprehension levels. These results highlight the critical role of vocabulary development in enhancing reading comprehension skills among Grade 6 learners in this specific context. These findings underscore the need for targeted interventions and literacy programs that focus on expanding students' vocabulary knowledge to improve their overall reading ability. Educators and policymakers in Tumauni South District should consider implementing strategies to enhance vocabulary instruction and provide more opportunities for students to engage with diverse texts to build their word knowledge and comprehension skills.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that educators and policymakers in the Tumauni South District prioritize vocabulary development as a key strategy for improving reading comprehension among Grade 6 learners. The strong correlation between vocabulary level and reading comprehension suggests that implementing targeted vocabulary instruction programs can significantly enhance students' overall reading ability. These programs should focus on expanding students' word knowledge through diverse reading materials and interactive learning activities. Additionally, teachers should be trained to effectively integrate vocabulary instruction into daily lessons across various subjects. It is also advisable to regularly assess students' vocabulary levels and reading comprehension skills in order to monitor progress and adjust teaching strategies accordingly. Furthermore, creating a language-rich environment, both in school and at home, through initiatives such as school-wide reading campaigns and parent engagement programs could further support vocabulary acquisition and reading proficiency. By addressing this vocabulary gap, educators can potentially improve students' reading comprehension skills, ultimately enhancing their academic performance in all subjects.

Compliance with the Ethical Standards

This is a declaration by the author in his own words, and in paragraph form which includes compliance with obtaining informed consent, the respondents' freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents' well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

Acknowledgments

The author acknowledges those who contributed to the success of this research.

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